

DAMAGE ACCUMULATION IN A $[0,90]_{2s}$ GFRP UNDER STATIC
AND FATIGUE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Stiffness reduction associated with damage build-up has been studied under both static and fatigue loading for a commercially available $[0,90]_{2s}$ glass fibre reinforced epoxy laminate. The damage build-up in terms of increasing transverse ply crack density was monitored for all three 90° plies in the laminate, i.e. the thicker, centre ply and the two thinner, outer ones, and significant observations were recorded for the two loading modes. A shear-lag type model was used in conjunction with the rule-of-mixtures to analyze the results and the predictions were shown to be in good agreement with the experimental data up to the onset of delamination.

KEYWORDS : laminate, tensile, fatigue, transverse cracking, stiffness reduction

1. INTRODUCTION

The damage build-up in laminates containing 90° plies, particularly cross-ply laminates of the type $[0_m,90_n]_s$, under both static and fatigue loading has been the subject of numerous studies. Much of the effort has been concentrated in the area of developing models based on the gradual change of a deterministic material property ("wear-out models") to predict the damage build-up during loading, and, thence, to establish the residual strength and life of these laminates.

The usefulness of stiffness reduction as a damage analogue in laminates has been pointed out by many workers including Highsmith and Reifsnider[1] and Daniel et al.[2]. Not only can

stiffness measurements be taken constantly in a non-destructive manner, but good correlation between stiffness degradation and damage accumulation has also been reported. It is generally noted that as loading progresses, either as increasing stress level for a quasi-static test or as increasing number of cycles for a fatigue test, the crack density increases until it reaches some stable value termed the Characteristic Damage State (CDS)[3]. During this process the stiffness decreases correspondingly until it reaches a stable value.

It is noteworthy that off-axis laminates exhibit different damage patterns when loaded statically and in fatigue[4,5,6]. Generally, a more dispersed damage pattern occurs under fatigue loading with the presence of delamination and longitudinal cracking. It has been suggested that the initiation and propagation of longitudinal cracks is connected to fatigue alone, and that a certain stress level is required to initiate them[4]. The density and rate of accumulation of fibre fractures for specimens loaded under these two modes have also been observed to differ substantially[5].

In the present work the longitudinal stiffness of a $[0,90]_{2s}$ glass/epoxy laminate is monitored in relation to transverse ply cracking while subjected to static and to fatigue loading. A model previously developed to relate stiffness to crack spacing in similar laminates is used in conjunction with the rule-of-mixtures to analyze these results.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

A schematic diagram of the specimen used in this programme is shown in Figure 1. The specimens were cut from 1m^2 laminate sheets which were fabricated from Fibredux 913G-E-5-30 unidirectional prepregs and autoclave cured using the vacuum bag system.

The quasi-static tension tests were carried out on a 50KN capacity screw driven Schenk Trebel testing machine in a displacement-controlled mode, employing a crosshead speed of 0.3 mm/min which resulted in a loading rate of ~ 0.25 KN/sec. Load-controlled fatigue tests, on the other hand, were carried out using a 100KN capacity Mayes servo-hydraulic testing machine at a frequency of 5Hz and stress ratio, $R = \sigma_{\min}/\sigma_{\max}$, of 0.5. The maximum cycling stress employed was 0.7 of the mean ultimate static stress. This gave a loading rate of ~ 30 KN/sec. Note that both loading rates are approximate values.

Stiffness reduction versus crack density was monitored in both the thick and thin transverse plies for 2 tensile (I & II) and 2 fatigue (A & B) specimens and this was carried out through periodic interruptions to the tests for measurements to be taken. The tangent modulus was calculated from stress-strain curves at a predetermined stress level, which was kept constant for all tests and was well below the damage threshold. Strain measurements were made using strain gauges.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Damage development

3.1.1 Static tests The mean ultimate static stress (σ_f) and failure strain (ϵ_f) of the laminate were determined from 4 samples to be $350 \pm 7 \text{MPa}$ and $1.25 \pm 0.04\%$, respectively. The stress-strain curves exhibited the typical non-linearity for a GFRP[6] and as such the mean initial Young's modulus (E_0) was calculated at the predetermined stress level of 40MPa to be $32.2 \pm 0.34 \text{GPa}$.

Damage development monitored for specimens I & II revealed that the first damage mode to occur is the formation of transverse ply cracks (TPC). Transverse cracking first occurs in the thicker, centre ply at stresses round about $0.7\sigma_f$ but as load increases TPCs start to form in the two thinner, outer plies as well (see Figure 2). These cracks initiate from fibre debonding at/near fibre-matrix interfaces : debonds form and subsequently coalesce, becoming a TPC nucleus. On further loading, the nucleus propagates across the whole transverse ply section to form a macro-crack. The initiation and development of transverse cracking are dictated by the thickness of the cracking ply as well as the stiffness of the adjacent plies. Parvizi et al.[7] and Bader et al.[8] demonstrated that for transverse plies sandwiched between stiffer plies and having thicknesses below a certain threshold value cracking could be constrained or even completely suppressed, if the cracking ply is sufficiently thin. A simple energy criterion is used to show that the minimum first cracking strain, ϵ^*_{\min} , increases as the transverse ply thickness decreases. The presence of constrained cracking is evident in specimens I & II, and in A & B as well, by shining a light through the translucent laminate which shows a series of cracks of different lengths. This is further confirmed by slightly polishing the edge of a specimen after counting the cracks and then making another count, which results in a lower figure.

Note that cracking is also more rapid in the thick ply than in the thin ones. No longitudinal splitting was recorded and delamination occurred just before the onset of failure.

3.1.2 Fatigue tests Under fatigue loading there is some indication that cracking has started in the thick ply first and this is shown by extrapolating the two graphs in Figure 3 back to the intercept on the abscissa. (These points, however, are not identical for specimens A & B probably due to defects present in the specimens prior to testing.) Thus the initial incidence of TPCs could again be said to agree with the energetics constraint mechanism model, albeit with some scepticism. As in the static case, cracking is more rapid in the thick ply than in the thin ones.

In Figure 3 also it is clear that after a certain number of cycles, depending on the

transverse ply thickness, the damage build-up follows part or all of a 4-stage development. Initially there are no TPCs (Stage I), but as cycling progresses rapid crack accumulation occurs (Stage II) followed by a more gradual rate (Stage III) before finally reaching a plateau (Stage IV). The absence of the fourth stage in the case of the thin plies is believed to be simply that they follow this development more slowly than the thick ply.

Boniface and Ogin[9] have demonstrated that the point at which transverse cracking starts in a laminate loaded under fatigue is dependent on the maximum fatigue stress. They found that cracking starts after the first cycle at maximum fatigue stresses above the static cracking threshold whereas several hundred cycles are needed when the maximum fatigue stress is below that threshold. Hence the maximum fatigue stress dictates the presence of Stage I and, for specimens A & B, it was somewhat below the static cracking threshold.

The onset of Stage II corresponds to the start of transverse cracking. After initial crack formation the rate of increase of crack density is high but subsequently slows down with increasing number of cycles corresponding to Stage III. This transition point is due to the decreasing local stresses between two cracks as their density increases, thence making it more difficult for cracks to initiate[10,11].

Stage IV corresponds to the CDS; this stable state is a laminate property and it is thought to be the same for both static and cyclic loading[3]. Note that the crack density of the thick ply for the tensile specimens at failure ($\sigma = \sigma_f$) is only in the region of 25-30% of the CDS observed in the fatigue test (i.e. 15 cracks/cm) which is consistent with the shear lag prediction[12] of 14.9 cracks/cm (normalized stress = 0.9995). Although the viscoelastic behaviour of the resin matrix could inhibit the formation of a crack[5], this discrepancy in crack density clearly indicates that there is a genuine fatigue crack propagation effect. The initiation of small debonds at weak fibre-matrix interfaces occurs at stresses below the static cracking threshold. Normally, under static conditions a debond would not grow into a crack, unless additional load is applied. However, under fatigue loading progressive extension of the debond can take place as the number of cycles increases via minute fractures caused by the successive 'opening' and 'closing' of the flaw. Eventually the grown debonds become long enough to permit monotonic failure across the remaining ply thickness to form a crack. This action could well be enhanced by the significantly higher loading rate employed for the fatigue specimens.

Internal delamination was detected but no longitudinal splitting was observed up to the point when the tests were terminated.

3.2 Stiffness degradation In the present work, the reduction in residual stiffness followed closely the observed damage development. For both specimens A & B (see Figure 4), the

initial rapid stiffness degradation which occurred between $0 - 5 \times 10^4$ cycles was accompanied by a sharp increase in crack density. This was followed by a more gradual reduction in stiffness corresponding to the reduced rate of increase in crack density. In specimen A, only a small delamination area, which did not grow very much throughout the remaining part of the test, was detected at approximately 2×10^5 cycles and this appeared to have negligible effects on stiffness degradation. In specimen B, however, a much larger delamination area was detected at approximately 4.5×10^5 cycles and this delamination grew substantially to bring about a sudden massive reduction in stiffness. As for specimens I & II (see Figure 2), the stiffness reduction was relatively small resulting from the low crack density accumulated. For comparison, the fatigue specimens achieved $\leq 7.25\%$ stiffness reduction after 3×10^5 cycles while the static specimens only achieve $\leq 2.75\%$ at the point of failure. Hence, stiffness reduction has a greater potential for monitoring the conditions in fatigue situations than in static.

It is interesting to apply a shear-lag analysis to relate the average crack spacing of the laminates to the stiffness reduction. The following equation, proposed by Steif (see [13]), relates the longitudinal stiffness reduction to the average crack spacing, $2s$, for an ideal $[0_m, 90_n]_s$ laminate with a uniform crack array (i.e. crack density = $1/2s$):

$$\frac{[E]}{[E_0]} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{E_0}{E_l} \left[\frac{b+d}{b} - \frac{E_l}{E_0} \right] \frac{\tanh \lambda s}{\lambda s}} \quad \text{where} \quad \lambda^2 = \frac{\alpha G (b+d) E_0}{d^2 b E_l E_t} \quad (1.1)$$

E_0 and E are respectively the axial Young's moduli of the uncracked and damaged laminate, while E_l and E_t are the longitudinal and transverse plies' axial Young's moduli. G represents the shear modulus of the transverse plies in the axial direction, and b and d are thicknesses of the longitudinal and transverse plies, respectively. For the present work load transfer along the longitudinal and transverse ply interface away from a TPC is assumed to be linear, i.e. $\alpha=1$.

Since the laminate has more than one 90° ply, and they are of different thickness, the contribution of each of them towards the overall stiffness reduction in the laminate due to matrix cracking has to be worked out separately. By treating the laminate as 3 separate $[0, 90, 0]$ laminates, or "sub-laminates", as shown in Figure 5, equation (1.1), in conjunction with the rule-of-mixtures, is adopted for this analysis.

From equation (1.1), we have for the thin sub-laminate :

$$\left[\frac{E}{E_0} \right]_1 = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{E_{01}}{E_{l1}} \left[\frac{b_1+d_1}{b_1} - \frac{E_{l1}}{E_{01}} \right] \frac{\tanh \lambda_1 s}{\lambda_1 s}} \quad \text{where} \quad \lambda_1^2 = \frac{\alpha G (b_1+d_1) E_{01}}{d_1^2 b_1 E_{l1} E_{t1}} \quad (1.1a)$$

and for the thick sub-laminate :

$$\left[\frac{E}{E_{02}} \right]_2 = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{E_{02}}{E_l} \left[\frac{b_2+d_2}{b_2} - \frac{E_l}{E_{02}} \right] \frac{\tanh \lambda_2 s}{\lambda_2 s}} \quad \text{where} \quad \lambda_2^2 = \frac{\alpha G(b_2+d_2) E_{02}}{d_2^2 b_2 E_l E_t} \quad (1.1b)$$

Hence, by combining equations (1.1a) and (1.1b) using the rule-of-mixtures, we arrive at :

$$\left[\frac{E}{E_0} \right]_{\text{Laminate}} = \frac{5}{8} \left[\frac{E}{E_{01}} \right]_1 + \frac{3}{8} \left[\frac{E}{E_{02}} \right]_2 \quad (1.2)$$

The following values are used for the analysis :

E_l	E_t	G	E_{01}	λ_1	E_{02}	λ_2
45.3GPa	15.0GPa	6.2GPa	33.2GPa	11.4X10 ³ /m	25.1GPa	6.6X10 ³ /m

(N.B. At least 3 specimens were tested in each case to obtain average values for E_l , E_t and G. E_{01} and E_{02} were determined using the rule-of-mixtures.)

Figures 2 and 4 show the predicted stiffness reduction in terms of E/E_0 as a function of applied load and number of cycles, respectively, alongside the experimental results. The experimental data lie below the predicted values indicating that the model underestimates the actual stiffness reduction and this is due to several reasons. It is clear that the model only predicts stiffness reduction as a result of transverse cracking. Although no systematic work has been done on fibre breakage, it is obvious that this damage mode is present in the 0° plies, especially in the later stages of the tests. In addition, the assumption in the analysis that the transverse plies have a uniform crack array is also not fully satisfied. This is especially so in the thin plies as shown in Figure 6. The rather crude way of sub-dividing the laminate could be refined; this requires a better understanding of how the internal stresses are redistributed during cracking in the various plies.

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Stiffness reduction associated with damage build-up has been studied under both static and fatigue loading for a [0,90]_{2S} GFRP laminate. The following conclusions are drawn from the work.

- 1) TPC is the first and dominant damage mode to occur the laminates.
- 2) Under static loads cracking in the thick ply precedes the thin ones. The same appears to be the case in fatigue, although cracking starts almost simultaneously in both the thick and thin plies in fatigue.
- 3) In both cases cracking is more rapid in the thick ply.
- 4) After a certain number of cycles, depending on the transverse ply thickness, the damage build-up in the fatigue specimens follows part or all of a 4-stage development comprising a crack free region, then an initial fast crack build-up region, followed by a more gradual increase in TPC density before finally reaching

- a stable state corresponding to the CDS.
- 5) While a load of $\sim 0.7\sigma_f$ is not sufficient to produce a substantial number of TPCs in the static mode, repeated applications of this load do induce extensive transverse cracking.
 - 6) A close relationship exists between stiffness reduction and damage build-up in the laminates.
 - 7) A shear-lag analysis used in conjunction with the rule-of-mixtures is able to describe the experimental data satisfactorily up to the onset of delamination.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Thanks are due to British Gas plc and the Committee of Vice-Chancellors and Principals for the funding of KHL, and to British Gas plc and the Fellowship of Engineering for support for JEK. The authors are also grateful to Mr. C. Young of Ciba-Geigy, Duxford for supplying the materials and to Professor D. Hull, FRS, FEng for provision of research facilities.

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FIGURE 1. Schematic diagram of the specimen geometry

FIGURE 5. Schematic diagram of the $[0,90]_{2S}$ laminate

FIGURE 3. Plots of crack density versus log number of cycles for the fatigue specimens

FIGURE 2. Correlation between damage build-up and stiffness reduction for the tensile specimens

FIGURE 4. Correlation between damage build-up and stiffness reduction for the fatigue specimens

FIGURE 6. The typical crack pattern observed in the fatigue specimens